

Synthesis of Chromones. Part II. Condensation of Nitrophenols with Alkyl Acetoacetic Esters.

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In order to find a satisfactory explanation of the causes of Simonis synthesis of chromones from phenols and alkyl acetoacetic esters using phosphorus pentoxide as the condensing agent, the reaction has been extended to nitrophenols and phenol carboxylic acids. It is remarkable that phenols possessing a negative substituent such as NO_2 and COOH which do not respond at all to Pechmann's reaction (Clayton, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 93, 2108; Pechmann, *Ber.*, 1899, 32, 3681), produce chromones, though with extremely poor yield, when condensed with the alkyl acetoacetic esters by means of phosphorous pentoxide. The nitrochromones are described in this paper, while the chromone-carboxylic acids will form the subject of the next communication.

The nitrophenols react with the alkyl acetoacetic esters with explosive violence and deeply coloured resinous products are invariably formed. Of the three nitrophenols, *m*-nitrophenol gives the best yield. The nitrochromones derived from *m*-nitrophenol may be 5- or 7-nitro-compounds and as attempts to establish the constitution by hydrolytic decomposition have not been successful, they are now provisionally described as 7-nitro-compounds. With *o*-nitrophenol no product could be isolated but it is desired to repeat the condensation using solvents.

These nitrochromones contain a reactive methyl group in 2-position and hence can readily be condensed with the aldehydes in presence of alcoholic sodium ethoxide and are thereby distinguished from the isomeric 4-methylcoumarins. The presence of a nitro group does not in any way lower the reactivity of the methyl group.

The work continued by the author in this line leads to the following conclusions:—

(1) *Pechmann's reaction*.—If the phenol reacts with a β -ketonic ester in presence of sulphuric acid, it will form always a

coumarin, any α -substituent in the acetoacetic ester molecule having no effect in the case of resorcinol, orcinol, pyrogallol, phloroglucinol and α -naphthol, which always show a marked tendency to form coumarins with good yield. *P*- and *m*-cresols form coumarins with unsubstituted acetoacetic ester, but with substituted ester the yield diminishes and no reaction takes place when substituents are heavy such as, propyl, isopropyl and isobutyl, due probably to the non-enolisation of the esters. *o*-Cresol, nitrophenols and phenol-carboxylic acids do not react at all.

(2) *Simonis reaction*.—By using phosphorus pentoxide in place of sulphuric acid, phenols (*e.g.*, resorcinol, orcinol, pyrogallol, phloroglucinol, α -naphthol) which form coumarins readily with good yield using sulphuric acid, invariably give coumarins. Phenols which react with difficulty to form coumarins (*e.g.*, phenol, *p*-cresol, halogenated phenols) or do not react at all (*e.g.*, *o*-cresol, nitrophenols, phenol-carboxylic acids, guaiacol, hydroquinone) using sulphuric acid as the condensing agent, yield with phosphorus pentoxide chromones. *m*-Cresol reacts with ethyl acetoacetate to form coumarin in good yield with sulphuric acid, and it also forms coumarin with phosphorus pentoxide; but with substituted acetoacetic ester, *m*-cresol does not give a good yield of coumarin using sulphuric acid and so it forms a chromone with substituted acetoacetic ester in presence of phosphorus pentoxide.

The theoretical discussion regarding these reactions is reserved until further work.

EXPERIMENTAL.

General Method of the Preparation of the Nitrochromones.

Phosphorus pentoxide (25 g.) is gradually added with stirring to a well-cooled solution of the nitrophenol (20 g.) in the alkyl acetoacetic ester (10g.) and the mixture is very slowly warmed up to 60-70° when it gradually becomes pasty and frothing takes place. It is then heated on the boiling water-bath for about 1½ hours. If this initial heating be not slow and gradual, the reaction sets in with explosive violence and the temperature rises so much that the whole mass is charred especially in the case of *p*-nitrophenol. Phosphorus pentoxide (15-20g.) is again added to the deeply coloured mass and the heating continued for an hour more to ensure complete reaction. The cold product is then treated with ice-cold water and the black product extracted with ether. The ethereal extract is carefully

washed with 5 p.c. caustic potash solution to dissolve the unaltered nitrophenol and then with water to remove the excess of alkali. As the ether evaporates off, shining crystals of the chromone separate out, which are filtered off, washed with a little alcohol to remove the adhering oily impurities and finally crystallised from absolute alcohol. The nitrochromones are mostly sparingly soluble in alcohol and ether.

General method of the preparation of the styryl derivatives by the condensation of the nitrochromones with aldehydes.—The method is the same as that of Heilbron, Barnes and Morton (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 2569). The nitrostyrene derivatives are coloured yellow to brown and are highly insoluble compounds.

Chromones from p-Nitrophenol.

6-Nitro-2:3-dimethylchromone is prepared by condensing *p*-nitrophenol with ethyl- α -methylacetoacetate. It crystallises from absolute alcohol as shining prisms melting at 163° and is identical with the chromone prepared by Petschek and Simonis (*Ber.*, 1913, 46, 2014) by the nitration of 2:3-dimethylchromone. (Found: N, 6.6. $C_{11}H_9O_4$ N requires N, 6.39 per cent.).

6-Nitro-2-styryl-3-methylchromone, the condensation product of 6-nitro-2:3-dimethylchromone with benzaldehyde, crystallises from glacial acetic acid as yellow needles melting at 205°. (Found: N, 4.8. $C_{13}H_{13}O_4$ N requires N, 4.56 per cent.).

6-Nitro-2-methyl-3-ethylchromone is obtained by the interaction of *p*-nitrophenol with ethyl- α -ethylacetoacetate. It is sparingly soluble in ether and crystallises in needles from absolute alcohol, m.p. 184°. (Found: N, 6.4. $C_{12}H_{11}O_4$ N requires N, 6.0 per cent.).

6-Nitro-2-styryl-3-ethylchromone, prepared by condensing the chromone with benzaldehyde, crystallises in yellow needles from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 239°. (Found: N, 4.1. $C_{15}H_{15}O_4$ N requires N, 4.36 per cent.).

6-Nitro-2-methyl-3-propylchromone is prepared from *p*-nitrophenol and ethyl- α -propylacetoacetate. It is very much soluble in ether and is finally crystallised in long needles from rectified spirit, m.p. 125°. (Found: N, 5.9. $C_{13}H_{13}O_4$ N requires N, 5.66 per cent.).

6-Nitro-2-methyl-3-isobutylchromone, the condensation product of *p*-nitrophenol with ethyl- α -isobutylacetoacetate, crystallises from

rectified spirit in long needles melting at 96°. In this case an appreciable amount of black residue remains, which is insoluble in ether (Found: N, 5.8. $C_{14}H_{15}O_4N$ requires N, 5.36 per cent.).

Chromones from m-Nitrophenol.

7-Nitro-2:3-dimethylchromone is prepared by condensing *m*-nitrophenol with ethyl- α -methylacetoacetate. The reaction is vigorous in this case. It is crystallised from absolute alcohol in needles melting at 136°. (Found: N, 6.5. $C_{11}H_9O_4N$ requires N, 6.39 per cent.).

7-Nitro-2-styryl-3-methylchromone, the product of condensation of 7-nitro-2:3-dimethylchromone with benzaldehyde crystallises from glacial acetic acid in yellow needles melting at 258°. (Found: N, 4.8. $C_{18}H_{13}O_4N$ requires N, 4.56 per cent.).

7-Nitro-2-methyl-3-ethylchromone, prepared from *m*-nitrophenol and ethyl- α -ethylacetoacetate, crystallises in needles from absolute alcohol, m.p. 167°. (Found: N, 5.8. $C_{12}H_{11}O_4N$ requires N, 6.0 per cent.).

7-Nitro-2-methyl-3-propylchromone, obtained from *m*-nitrophenol and ethyl- α -propylacetoacetate, is crystallised from rectified spirit, m. p. 136°. (Found: N, 5.72. $C_{13}H_{13}O_4N$ requires N, 5.66 per cent.).

7-Nitro-2 (m-nitro)-styryl-3-propylchromone is prepared by condensing the above chromone with *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde. It crystallises from a large volume of glacial acetic acid, m.p. 256°. (Found: N, 7.23. $C_{20}H_{16}O_6N_2$ requires N, 7.36 per cent.).

7-Nitro-2-methyl-3-isopropylchromone, prepared from *m*-nitrophenol and ethyl- α -isopropylacetoacetate, crystallises from rectified spirit in needles melting at 133°. (Found: N, 5.74. $C_{13}H_{13}O_4N$ requires N, 5.66 per cent.).

7-Nitro-2 (m-nitro)-styryl-3-isopropylchromone, the condensation product of 7-nitro-2-methyl-3-isopropylchromone with *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde, crystallises from a large volume of glacial acetic acid, as light yellow needles which do not melt up to 270°. (Found: N, 7.61. $C_{20}H_{16}O_6N_2$ requires N, 7.36 per cent.).

7-Nitro-2-methyl-3-isobutylchromone, prepared from *m*-nitrophenol and ethyl- α -isobutylacetoacetate, is crystallised from rectified spirit, m.p. 158°. (Found: N, 5.44. $C_{14}H_{15}O_4N$ requires N, 5.36 per cent.).

7-Nitro-2 (*m*-nitro)-styryl-3-isobutylchromone, obtained by condensing 7-nitro-2-methyl-3-isobutylchromone with *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde, is crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 252°. (Found: N, 7.28. $C_{21}H_{18}O_6N_2$ requires N, 7.1 per cent.).

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